
JOB-DEMAND STRESSORS AND EMPLOYEE TASK PERFORMANCE OF MANUFACTURING FIRMS IN DELTA STATE, NIGERIA.

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ABSTRACT

This study investigated the relationship between job-demand stressors and employee task performance of manufacturing firms in Delta State, Nigeria. The study adopted a cross sectional research design. A total of three hundred and fifty (350) employees were selected from ten registered and functional manufacturing firms in Delta State, Nigeria constituted the population of the study. Simple random sampling method was adopted to select the manufacturing firms and Taro Yamen formular was used for sample size. Three hundred and fifty (350) questionnaire were distributed and two hundred and eighty (280) were returned. Out of the two hundred and eighty (280) returned, one hundred and eighty (180) were certified good, suitable after data sorting and cleaning. Tables, percentages, Spearman's Rank Order Correlation Coefficients with the aid of Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS version 25) was used for data presentation and analysis and hypotheses testing to examine the relationship between job-demand stressors and employee task performance of manufacturing firms in Delta state, Nigeria. The study revealed that there is positive and significant relationship between job-demand stressors and employee task performance of manufacturing firms in Delta State, Nigeria. This entails that work overload, unnecessary time pressure, lack of support from supervisor/co-worker, inadequate pay, job insecurity and co-worker careless mistakes have tremendous negative effect on the employee task performance. The study concluded that, the current reality in the manufacturing sector in Delta state, Nigeria has placed serious burdens and stress on employees that has impede on their efforts to accomplish their daily, weekly and monthly tasks as it is require by most manufacturing firms in Delta state.. The study therefore recommends that, manufacturing firms should promote work-life balance programmes and encourage flexible job

activities to enhance personal effectiveness and focus on meeting one's targets for the good of both employees and the organization.

Keywords: Job-demand stressors, communication proficiency, task knowledge and job-specific task proficiency

INTRODUCTION

Over the years, the manufacturing sector of Nigeria's economy is characterized by high job demand on employees due to inadequate machine availability. The manufacturing sector require modernization and automation to give employee the leeway and enrichment to take firm control over their processes and systems for efficient and effective accomplishment of tasks in order to achieve organizational goals in record time. The current reality in the manufacturing sector in Nigeria at large and in Delta state in particular has placed serious burdens and stress on employees in their efforts to accomplish their daily, weekly and monthly tasks as it is require by most manufacturing firms in Delta State. Employees have to grapple with the job demand and their personal factors to achieve their task requirements which obvious have impeded their overall performance.

According to Pradhan and Jena (2017), performance in the form of task performance comprises job explicit behaviors which include fundamental job responsibilities assigned as a part of job description. Task performance requires more cognitive ability and is primarily facilitated through task knowledge (requisite technical knowledge or principles to ensure job performance and having an ability to handle multiple assignments), task skill (application of technical knowledge to accomplish task successfully without much supervision), and task habits (an innate ability to respond to assigned jobs that either facilitate or impede the performance) (Conway, 1999). Therefore, the primary antecedents of task performance are the ability to do the job and prior experience (Pradhan & Jena, 2017). The skills, behaviours and expectations could be directly or indirectly be impacted by factors outside the control of the employees.

The competition in the manufacturing sector is stiff and at the centre of this competition are employees and technology. Employees are critical and crucial because goals could be achieve through and with employees. The goals of manufacturing firms cannot be achieved without employees' efforts and task accomplishment. Hence, in order to be effective and efficient and achieve goals in this competitive globalized environment, organizations need human capital with the best skills, capabilities, knowledge expertise, motivation and the right attitudes towards their work (Zeb-Obipi, 2018). Considering the reality in the manufacturing sector in Delta State, for the manufacturing firms to operate efficiently and efficiently, factors that may impede employee performance need to be resolve urgently.

According to Murali, Basit and Hassan (2017), job stress has become part of employee daily routine in modern day Nigeria workplace. In work settings, stress can be produced by an array of stressors, such as work tasks, psychosocial and organizational factors (Tamunomiebi & Mezeh, 2021). According to Lazarus (1976), stress occurs when there are demands on the person, which taxes or exceeds his adjustive resources. According to Somaz and Tulgan (2003) cited by Tamunomiebi and Mezeh (2021), some of the common stressors in Nigeria's workplace includes: conflict in the organization, the way employees are treated by their bosses/supervisors, lack of job security, company policies, co-workers who do not do their fair share, unclear

expectations, conflicting roles and boundaries, poor communication, inadequate control over assignments, inadequate pay and benefits, urgent deadlines, work overload, long hours and time pressure, complex tasks, lack of breaks, lack of variety, Uncomfortable physical conditions, relationship conflicts, co-workers making careless mistakes, dealing with rude customers, lack of co-operation, having too much responsibility for people, under promotion and lack of training. We also, noticed that most manufacturing firms suffers from, unavailability of modern equipment, lack of modern techniques and systems and structures.

The obvious effects of this experience in the manufacturing sector have placed employees on a corner. Viviers (1998) cited by Tamunomiebi and Mezeh (2021) explained that employees are expected to cope with their vulnerabilities silently and quickly in order to still meet up target and set goals. Chandan (1995) define stress as a state of mind which reflects certain biochemical reactions in the human body and is projected by a sense of anxiety, tension and depression and is caused by such demands by the environmental forces or internal factors that cannot be met by the resources available to the person. Stress is cost by a multitude of demands (stressors) such an inadequate fit between what we need and what we capable of, and what our environment offers and what it demands of us (Levi, 1996)

Stress has been called the “health epidemic of the 21st century” (Robbins & Judge 2007). Studies have shown that job-demand stress is a strong risk factor for precludes to cardiovascular disease (obesity, high blood cholesterol, high blood pressure) and of adverse cardiovascular events, such as heart attack and stroke. Job-demand stress also has adverse effects on workers' mental health, with an increased risk of anxiety, burnout, depression, and substance use disorders. Employees who are stressed at work are more likely to engage in unhealthy behaviors, such as cigarette smoking, alcohol and drug abuse, stealing, and poor dietary patterns. These stressors make employees experience performance dysfunction in organizational expectation and his/her own needs. Some studies have been conducted on work related stressors and employees performance e.g Pradhan and Jena (2017), Burman and Goswami (2018) and Tamunomiebi and Mezeh (2021), but there are paucity of empirical studies on job-demand stressors and employee task performance in the manufacturing sector. In view of this undeniable gap, the purpose of this study was therefore to empirically examine the relationship between job-demand stressors and employee task performance of manufacturing firms in Delta State, Nigeria

The specific objectives of this study include:

1. To examine the relationship between job-demand stressors and job-specific task proficiency of manufacturing firms in Delta State, Nigeria
2. To investigate the relationship between job-demand stressors and task knowledge of manufacturing firms in Delta State, Nigeria
3. To assess the relationship between job-demand stressors and communication proficiency of manufacturing firms in Delta State, Nigeria.

The research questions are as follows:

1. What is the relationship between job-demand stressors and job-specific task proficiency of manufacturing firms in Delta State, Nigeria?
2. Is there relationship between job-demand stressors and task knowledge of manufacturing firms in Delta State, Nigeria?
3. What is the relationship between job-demand stressors and communication proficiency of manufacturing firms in Delta State, Nigeria?

JOB DEMAND CONTROL THEORY

This is one of the baseline theories adopted for this research. This theory was propounded by Karasek and Theorell in 1990. This theory primarily explained how job characteristics influence employees' psychological well-being and work-related stress. The theory demonstrates how job demands can cause stress for employees, such as heavy workload, role ambiguity, and job-related strain. However, the model posits that individuals can manage these stressors through utilizing job skills that allow them to gain autonomy and control over their work (Karasek & Theorell, 1990). Tamunomiebi and Mezeh (2021) explained that the Job Demand Control theory is a situation-centered model which identifies psychological job demands and job control (or decision latitude) as two primary job sources which can lead to stress at work. Holmstrom, Molander, Jansson and Bergqvist (2008) defined job demands stressors as psychological stressors present in the work environment such as high working pace, high time pressure, difficult and mentally exacting work. This theory underpins that when employees have high levels of job demands, this creates stress. However, employees can decrease this stress through gaining greater job control and developing strong relationships with their colleagues and supervisor. The JDCS model works when you, as an employee, use the following principles:

- i. **Gain control over your job:** It is important that you gain autonomy in your job. This can involve making decisions on your own without asking for direction. This might require negotiating with your supervisor on gaining decision latitude in your work. You can obtain guidance from your supervisor on decisions yet still gain freedom in making decisions regarding ways in which to work. This might require negotiating with your supervisor on gaining decision latitude in your work.
- ii. **Gain support from your supervisor:** it is important to gain support from your supervisor because having helpful social interactions can buffer the impact of stress. Karasek and Theorell (1990) define job support as overall levels of helpful social interaction available on the job from both co-workers and supervisors. Supervisor support can influence your attitude towards your job, including job satisfaction, and commitment; in addition, if you have the support of your supervisor and co-workers you are less likely to show intention to leave the organization.
- iii. **Gain support from colleagues:** both supervisor and worker support are coping mechanisms to buffer stress. In fact, it is more important to gain support from your coworkers because their support is critical and immediate (Treiber & Davis, 2012). Moreover, the relationship that you have with your co-workers helps you to perform your specific task effectively and their cooperation can also be a source for companionship and motivation during teamwork (Kossek, Pichler, Bodner & Hammers, 2011).

CONCEPT OF JOB-DEMAND STRESSORS

According to Pediwal (2011), job stress is basically a mismatch between the individual capabilities and organizational demand. Job stress expresses itself differently in different work situations and affects the workers differently. In work settings, stress can be produced by an array of stressors, such as work tasks, psychosocial and organizational stressors (Tamunomiebi & Mezeh, 2021). Onwuzuiligbo (2015) defines stressors as sources of pressure and tension that create stress and they are grouped into three (3) major categories which: 1. Physical stressors

which are physiological or external factors. 2. Social stressors which arises from social interaction like death of loved ones, imprisonment, and loss of job, lack of support from co-workers or supervisor, etc. 3. Psychological stressors which consist of the intense negative emotions people experience and could arise from either physical or social stressors.

Factors directly link to the task affect employee performance either positively or negatively. Factors such as skill requirements, timeline, job design, quality and quantity and utilization and adoption of modern equipment, etc have effect on the job. The moment an employee cannot meet up the demand on the job, it becomes a problem for him or her. Excess workload, time pressures, lack of required skills, lack of transparent workflow and communication lines, lack of support from co-workers and supervisors, multiple tasks without commensurate compensation seems to impede employee task performance from employees responses. According to Cooper, Fried, Shirom and Gilboa (2008) in their study of job demand stress, suggested that the appraisal of any stressor reflects two basic dimensions: The first dimension, associated with threat or hindrance and second reflect challenges which cause stressors to employees and hinder their productivity in certain ways.

EMPLOYEE TASK PERFORMANCE

Performance is a multicomponent concept and on the fundamental level one can distinguish the process aspect of performance, that is, behavioral engagements from an expected outcome (Borman, & Motowidlo, 1993; Campbell et al., 1993; Roe, 1999). The behavior over here denotes the action people exhibit to accomplish a work, whereas the outcome aspect states about the consequence of individual's job behavior (Campbell, 1990). Borman, and Motowidlo (1997) defined job performance in the context of task performance as "effectiveness with which job occupants execute their assigned tasks, that realizes the fulfillment of organization's vision while rewarding organization and individual proportionately. Performance management is a means of increasing the engagement and motivation of employees by producing feedback, correction measures and recognition (Armstrong, 2012).

Pradhan and Jena (2017) has operationalized employee performance into contextual performance, employee task performance and employee adaptive performance. Hesketh and Neal (1999) cited by Pradhan and Jena (2017) define adaptive performance an individual's ability to acclimatize and provide necessary support to the job profile in a dynamic work situation. An effective adaptive performance necessitates employees' ability to efficiently deal with volatile work circumstances (Baard, Rench, & Kozlowski, 2014), for example, technological transformations, changes in one's core job assignment, restructuring of organization and so on. Contextual performance: According to Pradhan and Jena (2017), industrial psychologists have referred such non-job components as organizational citizenship behavior (OCB) or contextual performance that refers to voluntary actions of employees (Bateman, & Organ, 1983) that benefit employers intangibly.

Contextual performance is a kind of prosocial behavior demonstrated by individuals in a work set-up. Such behaviors are expected of an employee but they are not overtly mentioned in one's job description. These kind of unstated expectations are called prosocial behavior or extra role behavior. According to Motowidlo (1986), it is behavior that is (i) accomplished by a member of an organization, (ii) which is directed towards an individual, group, or organization with whom the member interacts while carrying out his or her organizational role, and (iii) finally such

behavior is performed with the intention of encouraging the betterment of individual, group, or organization towards which it is directed. Conway (1999) cited by Pradhan and Jena (2017) opined that, performance in the form of task performance comprises of job explicit behaviors which includes fundamental job responsibilities assigned as a part of job description.

Task performance requires more cognitive ability and is primarily facilitated through task knowledge (requisite technical knowledge or principles to ensure job performance and having an ability to handle multiple assignments), task skill (application of technical knowledge to accomplish task successfully without much supervision), and task habits (an innate ability to respond to assigned jobs that either facilitate or impede the performance). Pradhan and Jena (2017) opined that, the primary antecedents of task performance are the ability to do the job and prior experience. In an organizational context, task performance is a contractual understanding between a manager and a subordinate to accomplish an assigned task. Providing further explanation on task performance, Pradhan and Jena (2017) divided task performance into organizational task and entrusted task performance with two segments: technical-administrative task performance and leadership task performance. The expected job performance comprising of planning, organizing, and administering the day-to-day work through one's technical ability, business judgment and so on are called as technical-administrative task performance. Borman and Brush (1993) and Tripathy (2014) as cited Pradhan and Jena (2017) explained Leadership task performance as the role of setting strategic goals, upholding the necessary performance standards, motivating and directing subordinates to accomplish the job through encouragement, recognition, and constructive criticisms.

Kreitner and Kinicki (2008) contend that employees are motivated by having specific goals to work for and they perform better when they are aiming at difficult goals which they have accepted therefore, when they receive feedback of performance and hence a difficult goal that is important to an individual is a constant reminder to keep exerting effort in the appropriate direction. The evaluation of employee's performance reveals the contribution of an individual in the organization's objectives. People do not learn unless they are given feedback on the results of their actions. For corrective actions to take place feedback must be provided regularly and it should register both successes and failures (Pattanayak, 2009).

MEASURES OF EMPLOYEE TASK PERFORMANCE

Job-specific Task Proficiency

Job-specific skills are the required skills and abilities that are essential for success on the job. This is the determinant of work quality. Technical skills, also known as hard skills, are the skills that relate to a specific occupation. Individual performance is not stable over time. Variability in an individual's performance over time reflects (1) learning processes and other long-term changes and (2) temporary changes in performance. Individual performance changes as a result of learning. Studies showed that performance initially increases with increasing time spent in a specific job and later reaches a plateau (Avolio, Waldman, & McDaniel, 1990; McDaniel, Schmidt, & Hunter, 1988; Quiñones, Ford, & Teachout, 1995). Moreover, the processes underlying performance change over time. Job-specific skills are skills required for a particular job. They might be completely unnecessary for other jobs but are critical for that job. Performance on the factor job-specific task proficiency can be defined as the sum of the expected

values of all behaviors related to job-specific task proficiency that an individual carries out over some standard period of time.

Task Knowledge

Campbell (1990) describes the task performance components as a function of three determinants (1) declarative knowledge, (2) procedural knowledge and skills, and (3) motivation. 1. Declarative knowledge includes knowledge about facts, principles, goals, and the self. It is assumed to be a function of a person's abilities, personality, interests, and education, training, experience and aptitude-treatment interactions. 2. Procedural knowledge and skills include cognitive and psychomotor skills, physical skill, self-management skill, and interpersonal skill. Predictors of procedural knowledge and skills are again abilities, personality, interests, and education, training, experience, and aptitude-treatment interactions and additionally practice. 3. Motivation comprises choice to perform, level of effort, and persistence of effort. Job specific knowledge entails the primary skills and experiences an employee must possess to be able to perform the core job he/she is assigned to do which will enhance the efficiency and proficiency of the employee. Every task or job has responsibilities and outcome that is expected from the employee. The employee must have a hands-on grasp of what is required of him/her, the knowledge and the skill to do the job. There are key performance indicators manager uses to evaluate employees on their task and these evaluation indicators are typically contain in the job description.

Communication Proficiency

The importance of effective communication in the workplace cannot be overemphasized. It is fair to note that communication is the lifeblood of workplace performance, outside skills and availability of work tools.. Communication is derived from the Latin word "*communicare*" which means to share, or to make common (Weekley, 2007). Communication is defined as the process sending message, understanding and sharing meaning (Pearson & Nelson, 2000). Communicative competence encompasses a fluency in language user's, grammatical knowledge of syntax, morphology, phonology and the like, as well as social knowledge about how and when to use utterances appropriately. Communication in the workplace differs from other forms of communication. Communication takes place when the message send to the receiver is absorbed and understood and there is feedback. Communication is process of sharing ideas, information, feelings and emotions among members of an organization that ensures mutual. The communication may be diagonal, top-bottom or bottom-top. The prime key factor in communication is the relationship and interaction between participants. Furthermore, in communication, four key aspects play a critical and important role and they are; 1. The message 2. The process 3. The feedback and 4. The action that follows after the feedback. In context of task performance, employees need to acquire the ability to receive messages promptly, understand messages clearly and interpret messages to his/her level of comprehension and take action in line with the message. Employee has to possess the ability to communicate clear by putting his/her thought together and interact effectively with others within the organization cycle.

JOB-DEMAND STRESSORS AND EMPLOYEE TASK PERFORMANCE

Copious of studies in the past seems to suggest that, effective employee performance in Nigeria workspace is not possible without stress. According to Tamunomiebi and Mezeh (2021), employees are expected to cope with their vulnerabilities silently and quickly in order to still

meet up target and set goals especially if they must keep their jobs. Bad policies of government, economic externalities and high rate of unemployment have reduce the power of an average employee in Nigeria to demand for better work environment hence, employees have to find a way to cope with the stress or get fired without compensation in most cases. This stress comes in different ways. Some could be employee behaviour induced, organization related stress and environment induce stress. Stress exists in every organization either big or small, workplaces and organizations have become so much complex due to growth and expansion. Workplace stress has significant effects over the employees' job performance, and the organizations are trying to cope with this scenario (Somers, 1995).

Tamunomiebi and Mezeh (2021) carried out a study on workplace stressors and employee performance: A conceptual review. In work settings, stress can be produced by an array of stressors, such as work tasks, psychosocial, and organizational stressors. Reviews of studies done on physical and psychosocial stressors revealed that physical factors, such as repetitive movements, awkward postures, high force demands, work posture, vibration and psychosocial factors, such as low co-worker support, high quantitative demands, low job control and low job satisfaction are of importance. The organizations therefore should be concerned with identifying the workplace stressors and empowering their employees to deal with those stressors that cannot be completely eliminated. Stress is a universal element experienced by employees around the globe. Stress has become major problem for employer particularly in developing nations where the employer does not realize the impact of stress on employee performance. It is important to recognize and address properly job stress because it badly affects the employee's mental and physiological health. These factors lead to negative employee performance. Stress at work is seen as one of the major psychosocial risks of work. Work-related stress is one of the problems confronting employee.

Pradhan and Jena (2017) carried out a study on employee performance at workplace: conceptual model and empirical validation. The study explores the concomitant areas for extending the scope of employee performance as a major domain of human resource (HR) effectiveness. We have interviewed researchers and corporate practitioners regarding their understanding of performance at workplace. On the basis of literature and feedback from academicians and industry professionals, a conceptual framework along with 42-item instrument on employee performance was proposed for empirical validation. The instrument obtained empirical views from experts on its proposed dimensions and statements. The initial analysis of content validity ratio (CVR) of the instrument had resulted in 38 items having CVR value of 0.49 and above with 75 percent acceptability from expert analysis. The retained items were taken for field survey. In total, 361 executives from Indian manufacturing and service organizations responded to the 38-item employee performance scale. Exploratory factor analysis revealed three distinct factors of employee performance that constitute the new scale: task performance, adaptive performance, and contextual performance (TAC). Reliability study on the sample reported significant internal consistency on the total scale ($\alpha = 0.80$) along with the three subscales (α ranging from 0.80 to 0.91). The prescribed framework offers an inclusive understanding of the nature and subtleties of employee performance. It is proposed that, HR managers and organizational behavior (OB) practitioners must use the insights from the explored factors to create and maintain a better work environment.

Akbari, Akbari, Shakerian and Mahaki (2017) carried out a study on Job demand-control and job stress at work: A cross-sectional study among prison staff. Job stress can impose significant costs

to the workplaces and organizations due to some issues such as absenteeism, less productivity, and medical costs. Job overload and lack of decision latitude can lead to job stress. The current study aimed to investigate the job demands and control as predictor of job stress and its relationship, with some of the demographic characteristics of Iranian prison staff. Materials and Methods: This study was performed on 171 male employees working in four prisons located in Ilam, Iran. The sampling method was census and all four prisons' staff were selected to respond the Job Content Questionnaires. Finally, the data were analyzed using t-test or independent samples test as well as SPSS 20. Results: The highest amount of job demand (mean = 21.28) and the lowest amount of job control on average (9.76) were reported by those staff working in Darehshahr prison. There was also a significant relationship between job post and job control among the prison staff ($\beta = -0.375$, $P = 0.001$). Conclusion: The level of job stress reported by prison staff was high in this study mainly caused by high job demand and low job control, especially in Darehshahr prison staff

In view of the foregoing argument, the following hypotheses were drawn.

- H₀₁:** There is no significant relationship between job-demand stressors and job-specific task proficiency of manufacturing firms in Delta state, Nigeria
- H₀₂:** There is no relationship between job-demand stressors and task knowledge of manufacturing firms in Delta state, Nigeria
- H₀₃:** There is no relationship between job-demand stressors and communication proficiency of manufacturing firms in Delta state, Nigeria

Fig. 1.1 Conceptual framework of Job-demand stressors and Employee Task Performance of Manufacturing Firms in Delta State, Nigeria

Source: (Armstrong, 2012; Chandan, 1995 & Campbell, 1990)

METHODOLOGY

Research methodology should capture the type of research, unit of analysis and the time frame for the study (Ahiauzu, 2006). The purpose of this study was to investigate the relationship between job-demand stressors and employee task performance of manufacturing firms in Delta State, Nigeria. The study adopted a cross sectional research design. The population of the study comprises a total of three and fifty (350) employees selected from ten (10) registered and functional manufacturing firms in Delta State, Nigeria. Simple random sampling technique was adopted to select the list of firms and Taro Yamen's formula (1973) was adopted to determine the sample size from the population while Bowley formular (1964) was used to determine the administration of structured questionnaire to each organization. Data was collected through the use of well-structured research questionnaire. Three hundred questionnaires were distributed and two hundred and eighty (280) were returned. Out of the two hundred and eighty (280) returned, one hundred and eighty (180) were certified good, suitable after data sorting and cleaning. Tables, percentages, Spearman's Rank Order Correlation Coefficients with the aid of Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS version 25) was used for data presentation and analysis and

hypotheses testing to examine the relationship between job-demand stressors and employee task performance

Table 1.0 Names of firms, Respondents and Addresses

S/N	NAME	NO. RESPONDENTS	OF ADDRESSES
1	ANUDU PLASTICS LIMITED	35	26 AMAECHI ANUDU STREET, ASABA
2	COLEMAN TECHNICAL IND LTD	35	NNEBISI ROAD, ASABA
3	OLITE MANUFACTURING COMP	30	CARETIME OLITE RD, ASABA
4	PERMOLIT PAINTS NIG	20	469 NNEBISI RD, ASABA
5	PRESWIN NIG LTD	25	IBUSA-ASABA EXPRESSWAY, ASABA
6	SOUTHWOOD NIGERIA	30	459 NNEBISI RAOD, ASABA
7	ASABA TEXTILE MILL	50	DENNIS OSADEBAY WAY, DELTA STATE
8	EBENCO GLOBAL LINK LTD	40	WARRI, DELTA STATE
9	NEFKOM ALUMINIUM COMP LTD	35	OZORO, DELTA STATE
10	DELTA PACKAGING CO. LTD	50	354 OGORODE IND ESTATE, ASABA

Table 1.1 Questionnaire Administration

S/N	NAME	NO DISTRIBUTED	NO RETURNED	% RETURNED	NO NOT RETURNED	%NOT RETURNED
1	ANUDU PLASTICS LIMITED	35	25	71	10	29
2	COLEMAN TECHNICAL IND LTD	35	26	74	9	26
3	OLITE MANUFACTURING COMP	30	26	87	4	13
4	PERMOLIT PAINTS NIG	20	15	75	5	25
5	PRESWIN NIG LTD	25	20	80	5	20
6	SOUTHWOOD NIGERIA	30	24	80	6	20
7	ASABA TEXTILE MILL	50	36	72	14	28
8	EBENCO GLOBAL LINK LTD	40	38	95	2	5

9	NEFKOM ALUMINIUM COMP LTD	35	28	80	7	20
10	DELTA PACKAGING CO. LTD	50	42	84	8	16
	TOTAL	350	280			

Source: Field Research, 2025

DATA ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Bivariate Analysis

We used the spearman's rank order correlation coefficient tool at 95% confident level for data analysis. The tests cover hypotheses H_{01} , H_{02} and H_{03} which are bivariate and all stated in the null form. To this end, we based on the Spearman's Rank (ρ) statistics to carry out the analysis. The 0.005 significance level was adopted as the basis for accepting or rejecting the null hypotheses at ($p < 0.005$) or rejecting the null hypotheses at ($p < 0.005$).

Table 1.2: Relationship between Job demand stressors and Job-specific task proficiency

		Job demand stressors	Job-specific task proficiency
	Job demand stressors	1.000	.682**
Spearman's rho	Correlation Coefficient		
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.	.000
	N	180	180
	Job-specific proficiency	.682**	1.000
	Correlation Coefficient		
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.
	N	180	180

Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Source: Field Research, 2025

H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between job-demand stressors and job-specific task proficiency of manufacturing firms in Delta State, Nigeria

From the table above, the result shows that, the correlation co-efficient (ρ) between Job demand stressors and Job-specific task proficiency yielded ($r = 0.682$) which shows a positive relationship and it is statistically significant at ($\rho = 0.01 < 0.05$). This showed that there is a positive significant relationship between Job-demand stressors and Job-specific task proficiency of manufacturing firms in Delta State, Nigeria. To this end, based on the empirical findings the null hypothesis earlier stated is hereby rejected and the alternate hypothesis stated as, there is a significant relationship between job-demand stressors and job-specific task proficiency of manufacturing firms in Delta State, Nigeria is accepted. This explains that, job-demand stressors affect employee job-specific proficiency and productivity.

Table 1.3: Relationship between Job demand stressors and Task knowledge

			Job demand stressors	Task knowledge
Spearman's rho	Job demand stressors	Correlation Coefficient	1.000	.822**
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.	.000
		N	180	180
	Task knowledge	Correlation Coefficient	.822**	1.000
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.
		N	180	180

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Source: Field Research, 2025

Ho₂: There is no significant relationship between job-demand stressors and task knowledge of manufacturing firms in Delta State, Nigeria

According to the findings on table 1.3 above, the results shows that, the correlation co-efficient (rho) between Job demand stressors and Task knowledge yielded ($r = 0.822$) which indicates a positive relationship and it is statistically significant at ($\rho = 0.01 < 0.05$). This showed that there is a positive and significant relationship between Job-demand stressors and Task knowledge of manufacturing firms in Delta State, Nigeria. To this end, based on the empirical findings the null hypothesis earlier stated is hereby rejected and the alternate hypothesis stated as, there is a significant relationship between job-demand stressors and task knowledge of manufacturing firms in Delta State, Nigeria is accepted. This explains that, job-demand stressors affect task knowledge. Employee may have the require knowledge for the job but job-demand stress could make him/her not to be productive or perform as it is expected.

Table 1.4: Relationship between Job demand stressors and Communication proficiency

			Job demand stressors	Communication proficiency
Spearman's rho	Job demand stressors	Correlation Coefficient	1.000	.839**
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.	.000
		N	180	180
	Communication proficiency	Correlation Coefficient	.839**	1.000
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.
		N	180	180

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Source: Field Research, 2025

Ho₃: There is no significant relationship between job-demand stressors and communication proficiency of manufacturing firms in Delta State, Nigeria

From the result on table 1.4 above, it indicates that, the correlation co-efficiency (rho) between Job demand stressors and Communication proficiency yielded ($r = 0.839$) which shows positive

relationship and it is statistically significant at ($\rho = 0.01 < 0.05$). This showed that there is a positive significant relationship between Job demand stressors and communication proficiency of manufacturing firms in Delta State, Nigeria. To this end, based on the empirical findings the null hypothesis earlier stated is hereby rejected and the alternate hypothesis stated as, there is a significant relationship between job-demand stressors and communication proficiency of manufacturing firms in Delta State, Nigeria is accepted. This means that, job-demand stressors can negatively impact on employee task performance despite his/her communication expertise or proficiency.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

After careful investigation of the study variables, the study indicated that, there is a strong, significant and positive relationship between job-demand stressors and employee task performance of manufacturing firms in Delta State, Nigeria, using Spearman's order correlation co-efficient and at 95% confident interval. The finding of this study confirmed that job-demand stressors have negative influence on employee task performance in the manufacturing sector. The results of the hypotheses tests for 1, 2 and 3 on tables 2-4 shows that there is a strong, significant and positive relationship between job-demand stressors and employee task performance of manufacturing firms in Delta State, Nigeria. The correlation co-efficient of 0.682, 0.822 and 0.839 respectively showed the positive relationships and this entails that job-demand stressors have negative impact on employee task performance. The finding further aligned with the fact that, workplace stress has significant effects over the employees' job performance, and some organizations are trying to cope with this scenario (Somers, 1995). Similarly, Akbari, Akbari, Shakerian and Mahaki (2017) explained that, the level of job stress reported by prison staff was high in this study mainly caused by high job demand and low job control, especially in Darehshahr prison staff affected employee performance negatively.

The Nigeria manufacturing workspace is characterized by myriads of stressors without much attention from relevant bodies to mitigate them. According to Tamunomiebi and Mezeh (2021), some of the common stressors in Nigeria's workplace includes: conflict in the organization, the way employees are treated by their bosses/supervisors, lack of job security, company policies, co-workers who do not do their fair share, unclear expectations, conflicting roles and boundaries, poor communication, inadequate control over assignments, inadequate pay and benefits, urgent deadlines, work overload, long hours and time pressure, complex tasks, lack of breaks, lack of variety, Uncomfortable physical conditions, relationship conflicts, co-workers making careless mistakes, dealing with rude customers, lack of co-operation, having too much responsibility for people, under promotion and lack of training

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The current reality in the manufacturing sector in Nigeria has placed serious burdens and stress on employees in their efforts to accomplish their daily, weekly and monthly tasks as it is require by most manufacturing firms. Job-specific proficiency, task knowledge and communication expertise without proper job design, clear delineation of roles and expectations, adequate compensation and timely support from both supervisors and co-workers, employee may continue to experience stressors capable of impeding their performance and full potentials in the workplace.

From the findings, we make the following recommendations:

- i. Managers of manufacturing firms in Delta state should engage employees in regular training and workshop to clear their roles, expectations and timelines with adequate incentive to encourage high performers.
- ii. Manufacturing firms should promote work-life balance programmes and encourage flexible job activities to enhance personal effectiveness and focus on meeting one's targets.
- iii. Job design in the manufacturing sector should comprise some levels of autonomy and enrichment to give employees control over their tasks and personal life
- iv. Technology adoption and modernization of manufacturing processes will help eliminate some stressors along the way with friendly policies, hence managers should ensure the availability of modern equipment in their workplaces and training of employees to operate them
- v. Managers of manufacturing firms should advance adequate welfare package to compensate employees for the daily and monthly discomfort they go through outside their normal routine to achieve organizational goals.

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